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Summary Report of Task 8.2 Activities

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WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level

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Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Received]
Coordinator	Marika Kolossa-Gehring	UBA	28/10/2020 21/07/2020
Grant Signatory	Helena Looström Urban	SEPA	21/07/2020

Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Approved]
Pillar Leader	Argelia Castaño	ISCI	21/07/2020
Work Package Leader	Ovnair Sepai	DH-PHE	20/07/2020
Task leader	Marika Berglund	KI	17/07/2020

Responsible author	Marika Berglund
Short name of institution	KI
Co-authors	Emilie Helte (KI), Agneta Åkesson (KI), 8.2 partners

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 2

Table of Contents

1	Authors and acknowledgements.....	3
2	Glossary.....	4
3	Abstract/Summary	6
4	Introduction	7
5	Task 8.2 data collection strategy	8
5.1	Description of work.....	8
5.1.1	Prioritised substances	8
5.1.2	Time points for time trend analysis.....	8
5.1.3	Age groups	8
5.1.4	European geographical regions	8
6	Results.....	10
6.1	Summary of Task 8.2 activities in 2019.....	10
6.1.1	Literature search for timepoint 1.....	10
6.1.2	DINCH	10
6.1.3	Phthalates	11
6.1.4	Bisphenols.....	13
6.1.5	PAHs	14
6.1.6	Organophosphate Flame Retardants.....	15
6.1.7	New analyses in the DEMOCOPHES biobank.....	18
7	References	21

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 3

1 Authors and acknowledgements

Lead authors

Marika Berglund (KI)

Emilie Helte (EH)

Agneta Åkesson (KI)

Contributors

WP8 partners

WP9 QAU

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 4

2 Glossary

1,2-Cyclohexane dicarboxylic acid diisononyl ester	DINCH
6-OH-Mono-propyl-heptyl phthalate	OH-MiDP
6-Oxo-Mono-propyl-heptyl phthalate	oxo-MiDP
7-Carboxy-(mono-methylheptyl) phthalate	cx-MiNP
7-OH-(Mono-methyl-octyl) phthalate	OH-MiNP
Bisphenol A, S, F	BPA, S, F
cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate-mono-(7-carboxylate-4-methyl)heptyl ester	cx-MINCH
cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate-mono-(7-hydroxy-4-methyl)octyl ester	OH-MINCH
cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate-mono-(7-oxo-4-methyl)octyl ester	oxo-MINCH
Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate	DEHP
Di(2-propylheptyl) phthalate	DPHP
Di-isononyl phthalate	DINP
Di-isononylcyclohexane 1,2-dicarboxylate	DINCH
Human Biomonitoring	HBM
Mono-(2-carboxymethylhexyl) phthalate	MCMHP
Mono-(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate	MEHHP
Mono-(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate	MEOHP
Mono-(2,7-methyl-7-carboxy-heptyl) phthalate	cx-MiDP
Mono-(2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl) phthalate	MECPP
Mono-(2,6-dimethyl-6-carboxyhexyl) phthalate	MCiOP
Mono-(3-carboxypropyl) phthalate	MCPP
Mono-(4-methyl-7-hydroxyoctyl) phthalate	7-OHMMeOP
Monobenzyl phthalate	MBzP
Mono-carboxynonyl phthalate	MCNP
Mono-cyclo-hexyl phthalate	MCHP
Mono-hydroxy-iso-butyl phthalate	OH-MiBP
Monoethyl phthalate	MEP
Monoethylhexyl phthalate	MEHP
Monobutyl phthalate	MBP
Monoisobutyl phthalate	MiBP
Monomethyl phthalate	MMP

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 5

Mono-n-butyl phthalate	MnBP
Mono-n-octyl phthalate	MnOP
Mono-n-pentyl phthalate	MnPeP
Mono-isononyl phthalate	MiNP
Mono-(oxoisononyl) phthalate	MOINP
OH-Mono-n-butyl phthalate	OH-MnBP
Organophosphate flame retardants	OPR
Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons	PAH

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 6

3 Abstract/Summary

Task 8.2 investigates data sources and gaps for the purpose of evaluating time trends in chemical exposure across Europe. This work aims to collect data for three time points, two age groups and four geographical regions.

For the first time point, chemical exposure will be assessed using existing literature data. For the second time point DEMOCOPHES biobank samples will be used and for the third time point, data generated by Task 8.1 will be utilised.

This report is a summary of all Task 8.2 activities carried out throughout 2019 and up to June 2020, which includes a literature search and initial review of biomonitoring data for the first time point and the progresses made in the access to and analyses of DEMOCOPHES biobank samples.

The links with the work of HBM4EU Work Package 9 (analysis of samples) and Work Package 10 (statistical analysis and data management) have been indicated.

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 7

4 Introduction

The aim of Work Package 8 (WP8) is to collect biomonitoring data on chemicals on the HBM4EU 1st and 2nd priority lists of substances and to assess related exposure over time in the general population across European countries.

Exposure will be assessed for three time points: 2006-2010, 2011-2013 and 2014-2019/2020, and data will be collected using three different strategies. For time point 1 (2006-2010), Human Biomonitoring (HBM) data which has already been published was identified through literature search. For time point 2 (2011-2013), DEMOCOPHES biobank samples are being accessed for retrospective analysis of chemical exposure and for time point 3 (2014-2019) we will rely on new harmonised HBM data collected in Task 8.1 (alignment of studies).

The work will be focused on two population groups (children age 6-11 years and adult women age 20-45 years) in four geographical regions of Europe (north, south, east and west). Provided that data is available, time trends will be assessed for Di-isononylcyclohexane 1,2-dicarboxylate (DINCH), bisphenols, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH), organophosphate flame retardants (OPFR), phthalates and cadmium (included in the 1st list of priority substances).

The aim of this report is to summarise all Task 8.2 activities performed throughout 2019, and to give an update on the progresses made in the analyses of DEMOCOPHES biobank samples.

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 8

5 Task 8.2 data collection strategy

5.1 Description of work

The aim of task 8.2 is to collect and generate biomonitoring data for selected HBM4EU prioritised chemicals that can serve as a basis for time trend analysis.

5.1.1 Prioritised substances

The substances of interest are selected from the HBM4EU 1st list of priority chemicals covered by the analytical quality assurance program established by WP9, and in alignment with the compounds analysed in Task 8.1. Detailed information on selected substances, metabolites of interest, and target group for each substance is outlined in Table 1. There is clearly a lack of data for the first time point for some of the metabolites, and thus, statistical time trend analysis will not be possible with the proposed strategy.

5.1.2 Time points for time trend analysis

Data for three time points will be investigated and collected.

1. 2006-2010: Based on scientific literature reviews
2. 2011-2013: Based on new chemical analyses of DEMOCOPHES biobank samples
3. 2014-2019/2020: Based on new results obtained in Task 8.1 aligned studies

5.1.3 Age groups

In alignment with two of the age groups included in the Task 8.1 alignment studies, the following age groups will be included in the time series:

1. Children 6-11 years
2. Women 20-45 years (to be compared with the aligned study women of 20-39 years)

5.1.4 European geographical regions

Exposure data on prioritised substances at each time point will be collected for 4 geographical regions. Europe was divided into 4 regions as outlined in report D8.1: A strategy to collect EU wide HBM data, and this categorisation will also be the basis for Task 8.2.

1. **North:** Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Iceland, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Sweden, UK
2. **South:** Croatia, Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain
3. **East:** Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Slovakia
4. **West:** Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Switzerland

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 9

Table 1: Proposed chemical compounds and metabolites to be included in time trend analyses

Chemical compounds	Metabolites	Target group
DINCH	OH-MINCH, cx-MINCH	Children
BPA		Women
BPS		Women
BPF		Women
PAH	1-hydroxynaphthalene, 2-hydroxynaphthalene, 1-hydroxypyrene	Women
OPFR	DPHP, BDCIPP, BCEP, BCIPP	Children
Phthalates	MEHP, 5OH-MEHP, 5oxo-MEHP, 5cx-MEPP, MEP, MBzP, MiBP, MnBP, MCHP, MnPeP, MnOP, OH-MiNP, cx-MiNP, OH-MiDP, cx-MiDP	Children
Cadmium		Women

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 10

6 Results

6.1 Summary of Task 8.2 activities in 2019

6.1.1 Literature search for timepoint 1

During 2019, a literature search, aiming to identify existing biomonitoring data on prioritised substances for the first time point (2006-2010), was performed. For DINCH, an updated search, identifying additional biomonitoring studies, was performed in 2020.

The search was carried out in PubMed with language and date restriction set to English or Swedish language, published 2004 or later. The following search terms were used:

- DINCH in combination with urine or Human Biomonitoring for DINCH,
- 1-hydroxynaphthalene, 2-hydroxynaphthalene, 1-hydroxypyrene or PAH in combination with urine or Human Biomonitoring for PAHs,
- bisphenol in combination with urine or Human Biomonitoring for bisphenols,
- organophosphate flame retardants or diphenyl phosphate in combination with urine or Human Biomonitoring for OPFRs,
- phthalate or phthalates in combination with Human Biomonitoring or urine for phthalates.

The search for biomonitoring data on cadmium has not yet been conducted and the searches for phthalate and bisphenol data are uncompleted. This work, together with reporting of obtained results, will continue in 2020.

6.1.2 DINCH

For DINCH, the substance of highest priority, only 6 studies¹⁻⁶ reporting biomonitoring data were identified. Biomonitoring data on children, which is the target population for DINCH, was not available for the specified time period.

Of the studies on women all were from the north (Sweden and Denmark)¹⁻³ or west (Germany)^{4,6} geographical regions. One of the studies, by Schütze et al. 2012⁶, was based on a sample of men and women with a mean age of 44, by Gyllenhammar et al. 2017³, had data partially collected after 2010. In the Gyllenhammar study, first void urine samples were collected from 30 pregnant women on an annual basis during the years 2009-2014, but results were only presented as averages for the entire sampling period.

Four studies assessing DINCH exposure among women in the relevant age group and within the specified time period were identified. Two of these, Shu et al. 2018¹ and Shu et al. 2019², used data from the same study population, the Swedish Environmental Longitudinal, Mother and child (SELMA) birth cohort. The first paper reported min, median, 95 percentile, max and geometric mean for crude and creatinine adjusted DINCH levels in first void urine samples for 1651 women¹. In the second publication, corresponding data was presented for 1674 women². In the first study, temporal trends were evaluated, and least square geometric means were reported for each year of sampling.

The two German studies identified, Schütze et al. 2014⁴ and Kasper-Sonnenberg et al. 2019⁵, were both based on samples from the German Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB). In the ESB, 24-hour urine samples are collected annually from 60 male and female individuals, age 20-30. Schütze et al. 2014⁴ analysed samples collected in the years 1999, 2003, 2006, 2009 and 2012 and reported crude and creatinine adjusted geometric means, median, 95 percentile and range of DINCH metabolites (MINCH, OH-MINCH, cx-MINCH, oxo-MINCH). Kasper-Sonnenberg et al.

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 11

2019⁵, reported corresponding data for OH-MINCH, cx-MINCH, oxo-MINCH and the sum of DINCH metabolites, for the years 2010, 2011, 2013, 2015 and 2017.

Table 2 provides a summary of all the studies assessing DINCH exposure identified in the search.

6.1.3 Phthalates

The literature search on phthalate biomonitoring data has not yet been completed, and the work will continue during 2020. However, a summary of the data identified in the 2019 search is provided in this section.

The results of the literature search indicate that there is a wealth of published biomonitoring data on phthalates, with samples collected within the specified time period for both target populations. The predominant part of the identified published material is from the west and north geographical region of Europe, and very little data has been found representing the south region, and none for the east region.

For the **south region**, two publications were identified from Spain, both assessing phthalate levels in spot urine samples among pregnant women and children enrolled in the Infancia y Medio Ambiente (INMA) project. The project consisted of four population-based birth cohorts in different Spanish geographical regions^{7,8}. In the publication by Casas et al.⁸, urine from a random sample of 120 pregnant women from all four cohorts and 30 children (age 4) in the Granada cohort, were collected in 2004-2008 and 2005-2006, respectively, and were analysed for 11 phthalate metabolites (MECPP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MEHP, MCP, MiBP, MBP, MBzP, MEP, MCiOP, cx-MiNP). Reported measurements included median and interquartile range.

In the study by Valvi et al.⁷ spot urine from 401 mothers in the Sabadell cohort who provided samples in both the first and third pregnancy trimester were analysed for 10 phthalate metabolites (7-OHMMeOP, MBzP, MEP, MiBP, MnBP, MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP and MCMHP). The measurements reported were creatinine adjusted geometric mean, min, max and percentiles 5th, 25th, 50th, 75th and 95th, by trimester.

From the **north geographical region**, nine studies were identified, of which three were from Sweden¹⁻³ and six⁹⁻¹⁴ were from Denmark. The Swedish studies by Gyllenhammar et al. 2017³, Shu et al. 2018 and Shu et al. 2019^{1,2}, have all already been described in the above DINCH section. Gyllenhammar et al. 2017 assessed concentrations of phthalate metabolites MEP, MnBP, MBzP, MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP, MCMHP, OH-MiNP, MOiNP, MCiOP, cx-MiNP and OH-MiDP, while the publications of the Shu et al. 2018 and 2019 reported MEP, MnBP, MBzP, MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP, MCMHP, OH-MiNP, MCiOP, OH-MiDP, cx-MiNP levels³.

Of the six Danish studies identified, all assessed urinary phthalate levels in children⁹⁻¹⁴. In the study by Boas et al. 2010⁹, 10 phthalate metabolites (MEP, MBP, MBzP, MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP, MnOP, MiNP, MCiOP) were analysed in spot urine samples collected in 2006-2007 from 845 4-9-year-old children, who previously had been part of a longitudinal birth cohort. Reported measurements included geometric mean, min, max, median and 25 and 75 percentiles of crude and creatinine adjusted phthalate metabolite levels, by sex. In the study by Langer et al. 2014¹⁰ crude levels of 8 phthalate metabolites, measured in first morning urine samples, collected 2008-2009 from 441 4-6 year old children were reported as geometric and arithmetic means, 5th, 25th, 75th and 95th percentiles. Results were presented separately for boys and girls. No creatinine or specific gravity adjusted levels were reported.

In two of the studies by Frederiksen et al 2011 and 2012^{11,14} phthalate concentrations in urine samples of girls (6-16 years) enrolled in the Copenhagen Puberty Study were reported. In the

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 12

2011 study, an additional group of adolescents were recruited (age 17-21), making the total number of participants 129. Concentrations of 11 different phthalate metabolites were measured in first void and 24-hour urine and reported as min max and 10th, 25th, 50th, 75th, 90th and 95th percentiles of MEP, sum of MBP, MBzP, sum of DEHP metabolites and sum of DiNP metabolites in first void and 24-hour urine, respectively. No corrections for creatinine were made.

In the 2012 study, concentrations of 12 phthalate metabolites (MEP, MiBP, MnBP, MBzP, MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP, MiNP, OH-MiNP, MOiNP, MCiOP) in first void urine among 725 girls age 6-19 were reported as mean, median, 95th percentile and range. The 2014 publication¹² was a summary report that provided an overview of existing Danish biomonitoring data in 4 different cohort studies, including the puberty study, with study participants of various ages and sex, collected in 2006-2012.

From the **west region**, 8 studies were identified, of which 5 were from Germany¹⁵⁻²⁰ and 2 from the Netherlands^{21,22}. German biomonitoring data was available for both target populations whereas the Dutch studies only assessed exposure among adult women. Among the German studies assessing phthalate exposure among adults, Fromme et al. 2007, reported phthalate metabolite concentrations in first void urine samples collected during 8 consecutive days in a mixed samples of men and women of various ages (14-60 years)¹⁵. Results were reported separately for men and women and included min, max, mean, 10th, 50th, 90th and 95th percentiles for concentrations of 11 phthalate metabolites (MnBP, MiBP, MBzP, MEHP, MEOHP, MEHHP, MECPP, MCMHP, MOiNP, OH-MiNP).

In another German study, by Göen et al. 2011¹⁶, concentrations of the same 11 phthalate metabolites were assessed in 24-hour urine samples from the German Environmental Specimen Bank collected in 2002, 2004, 2006 and 2008 (The German Environmental Specimen Bank is described in the DINCH section). Crude and creatinine adjusted medians, 95th percentiles and ranges were reported for each of the metabolites each year. A third German study by Koch et al. 2017²¹ analysed 300 urine samples from the German Environmental Specimen bank between 2007 and 2015 for 21 different phthalate metabolites. Measured samples were combined with data from Göen et al. 2011 and another previous (1988-2003)²² retrospective measurement campaign for a total of 1162 24-h urine specimens. Crude and creatinine adjusted medians, 95th percentiles and range were reported for each year of sampling, accordingly.

Another German study, by Kasper-Sonnenberg et al. 2012¹⁷, assessed exposure levels among 104 mother and child pairs (children 6-7 year olds and women mean age 39 years) in the Duisburg birth cohort study. Concentrations of 21 primary and secondary phthalate metabolites (MMP, MEP, MBzP, MnPeP, MiBP, OH-MiBP, MnBP, MCP, OH-MnBP, MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP, OH-MiNP, MOiNP, cx-MiNP, OH-MiDP, oxo-MiDP, cx-MiDP, MnOP) were measured in first void urine and crude results were reported separately for women and children as geometric means, min max, median and 95th percentile. Creatinine adjusted geometric means were also reported.

In a later publication by Kasper-Sonnenberg et al. 2014¹⁸, also partially based on the Duisburg birth cohort, biomonitoring data on the same 21 phthalate metabolites in first void urine of 113 8-9-year-olds of the Duisburg birth cohort and 352 8-10-year-olds in the Bochum cohort study were reported. Crude and creatinine adjusted geometric means, median and 95th percentiles were determined for each metabolite.

In the study by Koch et al. 2011²⁰, spot urine samples from 111 healthy primary school starters (5-6 years-olds) in Frankfurt were analysed for metabolites of 6 phthalates (MnBP, MiBP, MBzP, MEHP, MEOHP, MEHHP, MECPP, MCMHP, MOiNP, OH-MiNP, cx-MiNP, OH-MiDP, oxo-MiDP, cx-MiDP). Crude and creatinine adjusted geometric mean, median, 95th percentile and range of

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 13

each metabolite in urine were reported. A final study assessing phthalate exposure in children, by Becker et al. 2009¹⁹ utilised urine samples from the fourth German Environmental Surveys (GerES IV). 600 randomly selected GerES IV morning urine samples originating from 3 to 14-year olds were analysed for 11 phthalate metabolites (MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP, MCMHP, MnBP, MiBP, MBzP, OH-MiNP, MOiNP and cx-MiNP). Crude geometric mean, max, median 50th 90th and 95th percentiles were reported for each metabolite.

The Dutch studies identified in the literature search were both based on urine samples collected 2004-2005 within the Generation R Study, a population-based prospective cohort study of pregnant women. In the study by Ye et al. 2008²³, urine from a random sample of 100 women was analysed for 14 phthalate metabolites (MMP, MEP, MnOP, MCP, MnBP, MiBP, MBzP, MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP, MCMHP, MOiNP, OH-MiNP). Unadjusted and creatinine adjusted geometric mean, min, max and 5th, 25th, 50th, 75th, and 95th percentiles of urinary phthalate metabolite levels were reported. In the later study by Philips et al. 2020²⁴, median concentrations and interquartile range of 12 phthalate metabolites (MMP, MEP, MiBP, MBP, MEcPP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MCMHP, MCP, MBzP,) in spot urine samples from 1213 women in early and mid-pregnancy were assessed.

Table 3 provides a summary of all studies assessing phthalate exposure that were identified in the literature search.

6.1.4 Bisphenols

The search for bisphenol biomonitoring data has not yet been completed, and the work will continue during 2020. This section summarises the results of the 2019 search.

For bisphenols we were able to identify studies providing biomonitoring data for both target populations within the relevant time period. However, most studies were from the west and north region (predominantly Germany, Denmark and The Netherlands), little data (in adults only) was available for the south region and no data representing the east region was found.

Out of the three bisphenols of relevance, almost all studies were focusing on bisphenol A (BPA). In total, 12 studies were identified and of these 4 were from the north (Denmark and Sweden), 2 from the south (Spain and Cyprus) and 6 from the west region (Germany and The Netherlands). Some of the studies have already been described in the DINCH and phthalate sections and include Gyllenhammar et al. 2017³ (North, women, BPA, F and S), Frederiksen et al. 2014¹² (North, children, Bisphenol A), Becker et al. 2009¹⁹ (West, children, BPA), Kasper-Sonnenberg et al. 2014¹⁸ (West, children, BPA), Ye et al. 2008²³ (west, women, BPA), Philips et al. 2020²⁴ (west, women, BPA), Casas et al. 2011⁸ (South, children and women, BPA).

One additional study from the south region (Cyprus) by Makris et al. 2013²⁵ assessed urinary BPA concentrations in spot urine samples of 35 healthy adults (predominantly students, 21-55 years), who were largely relying on polycarbonate bottled water to satisfy potable needs. Urine samples were collected during two warm summer days. Results were reported as creatinine adjusted median concentrations and interquartile range.

Representing the north region, we identified one additional study by Frederiksen et al. 2013²⁶, originating from Denmark. In this study, the investigators assessed urinary BPA excretion in the same 129 children and adolescents as in their phthalate study from 2011¹¹. Concentrations and total amounts were reported for one 24-hour urine collection and two first void samples collected during two consecutive days as mean, min, max 10th 25th 50th 75th 90th and 95th percentiles.

From the west region, we found two additional studies reporting bisphenol biomonitoring data, Kasper-Sonnenberg et al. 2012¹⁷ and Moos et al. 2014²⁷. In the study by Kasper-Sonnenberg et al. 2012, BPA concentration was measured in 208 first void urine samples of 104 mother-child

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 14

pairs of the Duisburg birth cohort study (the cohort is described in the phthalate section). Crude and creatinine adjusted geometric means, min, max, median and 95th percentiles were reported separately for women and children as well as for boys and girls. Moos et al. 2014 also presented biomonitoring data on BPA based on the Duisburg birth cohort participants but the samples were further complemented with spot urine samples from 39 male volunteers (18–64 years), collected in 2010 and 2011 (i.e. after the end of the first time period). Lastly, Koch et al. 2012²⁸ measured concentrations of BPA in 600 24-h urine samples between 1995 and 2009 from the German environmental specimen bank. Geometric means, medians, 95th percentiles and range of concentrations (both crude and creatinine adjusted) were reported.

Table 4 provides a summary of all the identified studies which assessed bisphenol exposure.

6.1.5 PAHs

Studies providing biomonitoring data on PAH were mainly focused on 1-hydroxypyrene, although some also reported levels of 1-hydroxynaphtalene and 2-hydroxynaphtalene. Biomonitoring data for 1-hydroxypyrene was available for both age groups within the given time period but not for all geographical regions.

The only study representing the north region identified was the study by Gyllenhammar et al. 2017³, in which data was partially collected outside of the specified time period.

For the east region, 5 publications based on data from the Polish mother child cohort (Polanska et al. 2010²⁹, 2011³⁰, 2013³¹, 2014a³² and 2014b³³) were identified. The Polish mother and child cohort is a multicentre prospective cohort conducted in eight regions of Poland. Pregnant women were recruited 2007-2011 and urine samples were collected at 20-24 weeks of gestation. In the most extensive publication in terms of biomonitoring data, by Polanska et al. 2014a, mean, min, max median and 95th percentile of creatinine adjusted concentrations of PAH metabolites 1-, 2-, 3-, 4-, 9-hydroxyphenanthrene, sum of hydroxyphenanthrenes, phenanthrene trans-1,2-dihydrodiol, phenanthrene trans-9,10-dihydrodiol, sum of phenanthrene dihydrodiols, 1-hydroxypyrene, sum of 1,6- and 1,8-dihydroxypyrenes, and sum of 1-hydroxypyrene, 1,6- and 1,8-dihydroxypyrenes in urine of 104 non-smoking women were reported³³.

For the south region, four studies - one Italian and three Spanish studies, were identified. In the study by Cirillo et al. 2006³⁴ spot urine samples of 30 school children, 7-9 year old, from two different towns in the region of Campania, Italy, were analysed for 1-hydroxypyrene. Creatinine adjusted excretion levels were reported as means and standard deviations and results were presented separately by town. A second study focusing on children by Freire et al. 2009³⁵, assessed urinary 1-hydroxypyrene in 174 4-year-olds. Among the two studies focusing on adults, Llop et al. 2008³⁶, assessed concentrations of 1-hydroxypyrene in spot urine samples provided by 204 pregnant women enrolled in the INMA Valencia cohort (The INMA project is described in the phthalate section).

In the other study on adults, by Bartolomé et al. 2015³⁷, first void urine samples from 957 adults (older than 16 years) were analysed for 1-hydroxypyrene and sum of hydroxyphenanthrenes. Creatinine adjusted concentrations in terms geometric mean and 10th 25th 50th 75th 90th and 95th percentiles were reported both for the entire sample as well as by sex, age and smoking categories.

For the west region we identified three studies, of which two were based on the German Environmental Survey on Children (GerES IV)^{38,39} and one was in British adults⁴⁰. In GerES IV morning urine from 289 girls and 310 boys age 3-14 years was analysed for PAH metabolites 1-hydroxypyrene, 1-naphtol and 2-naphtol. Reference values together with median and 95th percentiles were reported in total and for smoking and non-smoking children separately. In the

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 15

study by Aquilina et al. 2010³⁷ concentrations of monophenolic metabolites of naphthalene, fluorene, phenanthrene, and pyrene were measured in first void urine samples from 100 non-smoking healthy adult volunteers in the United Kingdom. Results were presented as geometric means separately for subjects exposed to environmental tobacco smoke and non-exposed.

Table 5 provides a summary of all the identified studies which assessed PAH exposure.

6.1.6 Organophosphate Flame Retardants

There is a clear lack of published OPFR biomonitoring data sampled within the specified time period and the European region. Only one study was identified, in which sampling was partially performed after the end of the first time period (Gyllenhammar et al. 2017³). Thus, it will not be possible to complete the time trend analysis for OPFRs using the suggested three time points.

Table 2: Biomonitoring studies assessing DINCH exposure in 2006-2010 in the European population identified through literature search

Region	Country	Population	Year of data collection	Study (reference)
North	Sweden	1651 and 1674 pregnant women, respectively	2007–2010	Shu et al. 2018, Shu et al. 2019
North	Sweden	178 first time mothers, 20–41 years	2009–2014	Gyllenhammar et al. 2017
West	Germany	22 men and women (23–57 years)	2010	Schütze et al. 2014
West	Germany	Students (30 male and 30 female per year), 20–30 years	1999, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012	Schütze et al. 2014
West	Germany	Students (30 male and 30 female per year), 20–30 years	2010, 2011, 2013, 2015 and 2017	Kasper-Sonnenberg et al. 2019

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 16

Table 3: Biomonitoring studies assessing phthalate exposure in 2006-2010 in the European population identified through literature search

Region	Country	Population	Year of data collection	Study (reference)
North	Denmark	845 boys and girls, 4-9 years	2006-2007	Boas et al. 2010
North	Denmark	441 children 3-6 years	2008-2009	Langer et al. 2014
North	Denmark	725 girls, 5-19 years	2006-2008	Frederiksen et al 2012,
North	Denmark	129 children, 6-21 years	2007	Frederiksen et al 2011
North	Denmark	Children and adolescents from 3 different cohorts	2006-2008	Frederiksen et al. 2014
North	Sweden	178 first time mothers, 20-41 years	2009–2014	Gyllenhammar et al. 2017
North	Sweden	1651 pregnant women	2007-2010	Shu et al. 2018
South	Spain	391 pregnant women	2004-2006	Valvi et al. 2015
South	Spain	120 pregnant women and 30 4-year old children	2005-2008	Casas et al. 2011
West	Germany	Students (30 male and 30 female per year), 19-29 years	2002-2008	Göen et al. 2011
West	Germany	Students (30 male and 30 female per year), 19-29 years	2007-2015	Koch et al. (2017)
West	Germany	27 men and women, 14-60 years	2005	Fromme et al. 2007
West	Germany	113 and 352 children 8-10 years	2007-2008 and 2009-2010	Kaspersen-Sonnenberg et al. 2014
West	Germany	1790 children, 3-14 years	2003-2006	Becker et al. 2009
West	Germany	111 children, 5-6 years	2007	Koch et al. 2011
West	Germany	104 mother–child-pairs	2007-2009	Kaspersen-Sonnenberg et al. 2012
West	The Netherlands	100 pregnant women	2004-2006	Ye et al. 2008
West	The Netherlands	1406 pregnant women	2004-2005	Philips et al. 2020

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 17

Table 4: Biomonitoring studies assessing Bisphenol exposure in 2006-2010 in the European population identified through literature search

Region	Country	Population	Year of data collection	Study (reference)
North	Denmark	107 girls, 8-16 years	2007	Carlsson et al. 2018
North	Denmark	Children and adolescents from 3 different cohorts	2006-2008	Frederiksen et al 2014
North	Denmark	Children 6-16 and 19 adolescents 17-21	2006-2008	Frederiksen et al. 2013
North	Sweden	178 first time mothers, 20-41 years	2009–2014	Gyllenhammar et al. 2017
South	Cyprus	Adult students	2010	Makris et al. 2013
South	Spain	120 pregnant women and 30 children 4 year olds	2005-2008	Casas et al. 2011
West	Germany	104 mother- child pairs	2007-2009	Kasper-Sonnenberg et al. 2012
West	Germany	157 mothers, children and adults males	2007-2009	Moos et al. 2014
West	Germany	113 and 352 children 8-10 years	2007-2008 and 2009-2010	Kasper-Sonnenberg et al. 2014
West	Germany	1790 children aged 3 to 14 years and women	2003-2006	Becker et al. 2009
West	Germany	Students (30 male and 30 female per year), 19-29 years	1995-2009	Koch et al. (2012)
West	The Netherlands	100 pregnant women	2004-2006	Ye et al. 2008
West	The Netherlands	1406 pregnant women	2004-2005	Philips et al. 2020

Table 5: Biomonitoring studies assessing PAH exposure in 2006-2010 in the European population identified through literature search

Region	Country	Population	Year of data collection	Study (reference)
East	Poland	Pregnant women	2007-2011	Polanska et al. 2010, Polanska et al. 2011, Polanska et al. 2013, Polanska et al. 2014a Polanska et al. 2014b
North	Sweden	178 first time mothers, 20-41 years	2009–2014	Gyllenhammar et al. 2017
South	Italy	30 children, 7-8 years	2004	Cirillo et al. 2006
South	Spain	993 adults	2009-2010	Bartolomé et al. 2015
South	Spain	174 children, 4 years old	2005-2006	Freire et al. 2009
South	Spain	204 pregnant women	2003-2005	Llop et al. 2008
West	Germany	599 children, 3-14 years	2003-2006	Wilhelm et al. 2008 Schulz et al. 2009
West	UK	100 adult healthy volunteers	2005-2007	Aquilina et al. 2010

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 18

Table 6: Biomonitoring studies assessing organophosphate flame-retardant exposure in 2006-2010 in the European population identified through literature search

Region	Country	Population	Year of data collection	Study (reference)
North	Sweden	178 first time mothers, 20-41 years	2009–2014	Gyllenhammar et al. 2017

The statistical analyses will be performed by WP10 and will be based on aggregated data as described in Deliverable D10.10: Statistical analysis plan for the co-funded studies of WP8.

6.1.7 New analyses in the DEMOCOPHES biobank

The DEMOCOPHES biobank was selected as the basis for the second time point (2011-2013) on the grounds of that the study is well defined and harmonised across European countries. Several prioritised substances have already been analysed in the samples and results have been reported (seven phthalate metabolites, BPA, and cadmium). New analyses on remaining prioritised DEMOCOPHES biobank samples were undertaken in 2019 and in 2020. Ten partners have announced interest in performing new analyses and the progresses made are summarised in the table 7. For budgetary and other reasons, not all partners will do all metabolites of interest. There has been a delay in the new laboratory analyses of the DEMOCOPHES samples. Firstly, new analysis could not be planned or undertaken until approved laboratories were appointed (first list of laboratories was published in August 2019). Secondly, the pandemic among other things delayed transport of samples to laboratories out of the countries. Nevertheless, several analyses have been completed and the planned analyses, as displayed in Table 7, is assumed to be completed in the coming months. As today, there is still some lack of information regarding the possibility to analyse some of the metabolites by some of the partners.

Table 7: Summary on the progresses in the laboratory analyses of DEMOCOPHES biobank samples

Partner	Children	Women
North		
Denmark/UCPH		
Completed analyses	Phthalates, DINCH	Cd and BPA
Planned analyses	Not known	Not known
Sweden/SEPA/KI		
Completed analyses	Phthalates, DINCH, (OPFR*)	Cd, BPA, BPS, BPF, PAH
Planned analyses		
South		
Cyprus/ MOH-CY		
Completed analyses	Phthalates,	Cd
Planned analyses	DINCH, OPFR	BPA, BPS?, BPF?, PAH

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 19

Partner	Children	Women
Slovenia/JSI		
Completed analyses	Phthalates	Cd, BPA
Planned analyses	OPFR	
Spain/ISCIII		
Completed analyses	Phthalates	Cd, BPA
Planned analyses	DINCH	BPS, BPF
East		
Czech Republic/MU/SZU-CZ		
Completed analyses	Phthalates	Cd
Planned analyses	DINCH, OPFR	BPA, BPS, BPF, PAH
Poland/NIOM		
Completed analyses	Phthalates	Cd
Planned analyses	DINCH, OPFR	BPA, BPS, BPF, PAH
West		
Belgium/VITO		
Completed analyses	Phthalates	Cd, BPA
Planned analyses	DINCH, OPFR	Not known
Germany/UBA		
Completed analyses	Phthalates, DINCH, OPFR	Cd , PAH
Planned analyses		
Luxembourg/LNS		
Completed analyses	Phthalates, DINCH	Cd, BPA, BPS, BPF
Planned analyses		PAH

* Analyses have been completed, but outside HBM4EU QA/QC scheme (analysed at ULUND)

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 20

CONCLUSIONS

The review of data for the first timepoint is underway and will be completed by September 2020. There is a lack of data for the first time point for some of the metabolites, and thus, statistical time trend analysis will not be possible using the proposed strategy.

The data from the completed laboratory analysis of the DEMOCOPHES samples will be included in the IPCHEM platform (aggregated data), and individual data can be shared by data controller agreements between partners. The planned laboratory analysis of DEMOCOPHES samples (see Table 7) is currently being organised and will be completed in the coming months in collaboration with WP9.

In collaboration with Task 8.1 and WPs 9 and 10, the final time trend analysis will be reported for as many metabolites as possible.

AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 21

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AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 22

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AD8.5 - Summary Report on Task 8.2 activities	Security: Public
WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level	Version: 1.1
Authors: Berglund M, Helte E, Åkesson A	Page: 23

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